

JOB TRAINING: AN INSTRUMENT FOR ENHANCING EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR

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Abstract

This study examined on-the-job training and employee performance in the public sector. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from a stratified sample of 253 respondents selected using the Taro Yamane sample size method in a population of 689 senior non-teaching personnel at Ambrose Alli University in Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. The data was examined using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that all the items studied scored higher than the 2.5 cut-off mean. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) analysis results revealed that induction training has a significant impact on job satisfaction, whereas job rotation has a significant impact on employee commitment to work. The study found that on-the-job training improves employee performance in the public sector. The study advised that public organisations should use on-the-job training, specifically induction and job rotation, on a regular basis to improve employee performance

Keywords: *on-the-job, training, employee performance, public sector*

Introduction

In recent times, most organizations are striving towards technological innovations for cost benefits, job accuracy and faster service delivery but are giving less attention to employee training, forgetting that equipping the employees with desirable skills could lead to efficiency in job performance to bring about the desired level of productivity in organisation. Training is one of the most crucial human resource development practices that organisations should not neglect, because people may be drawn to high compensation and have a good working atmosphere, but if they lack the essential skills and experience to complete the tasks allocated to them, the organizational goal may not be achieved. In fact, training is a motivational instrument used by management to increase organizational performance, such as low labour turnover, job satisfaction, employee commitment, efficiency and productivity (Solaja & Oladimeji, 2019).

Training is a systematic technique that includes several activities aimed at changing employees' attitudes, behaviours, knowledge, and abilities through learning experiences in order to improve performance and productivity (Wajdi, et al, 2014). The quality of training an employee received may influence the quality of skills, talents, and expertise that he or she possesses, as well as the level of efficiency that can be demonstrated in job operation (Nwaeke & Obiekwe, 2017). Employee training is classified into two categories: off-the-job and on-the-job training. Off-the-job training is the type of training that employees receive outside of the workplace, whereas on-the-job training occurs within the organization to improve performance. On-the-job training promotes employee performance by exposing them to a wide range of new activities in various divisions of the company, allowing them to advance their skills and capacities. It also exposes the individual to actual job activities and promotes performance without interfering with the organization's day-to-day operations (Eeden, et al 2018).

Despite the importance of on-the-job training for organisational success, it is surprising that most organizations, particularly those in the public sector, do not prioritize on-the-job training. According to Osolaji and Oladimeji (2019), staff training in the Nigerian public sector is considered a waste of resources rather than an investment; as a result, most state-owned organizations in Nigeria rely on ad hoc training that is carried out in a haphazard manner to cut costs. The

consequence is that employee training in the public sector is somewhat haphazard due to insufficient planning. Given the consequences, the public sector is swamped with inefficient and underperforming staff (Edeh & Nwaji, 2017). Furthermore, Nwaeke and Obiekwe (2017) claimed that most organizations in the public sector have relied on off-the-job training, believing that personnel were fully trained before being hired into the organization. Thus, can it be considered that workers possess the required skills and experience they need to accomplish the tasks that would be given to them and can function properly in the absence of on-the-job training such as induction, coaching, job rotation, and others within the organisation? Perhaps this is why many organizations regard on-the-job training as irrelevant.

However, it is worth noting that this argument has continued to fuel scholarly debate about the impact of on-the-job training on employee performance in firms. Although evidence suggests that the relationship between on-the-job training and employee performance has received extensive attention, a review of the literature on human resource development practice in organizations revealed that the issue has not been thoroughly investigated in developing countries, particularly Nigeria. Thus, to the best of this paper's knowledge, very few studies on on-the-job training and employee performance in organizations have been undertaken in developing countries, with only a few in the public sector and none in Edo State of Nigeria. For example, Salini and Gosekwang (2015) investigated the effects of on-the-job training on employee performance at Riley's Hotel in Maun, Botswana. Adeba (2019) also researched the relationship between on-the-job training and employee performance at Ethiopia's Wollega University. Furthermore, Agufana (2022) investigated the impact of on-the-job training strategies on work performance at Kenya's Murang'a University of Technology. Furthermore, Mvuyisi and Mbukanma (2023) studied the effect of on-the-job training on employee performance at Walter Sisulu University in Mthatha, East London. On the other hand, Agbo (2020) explored the effects of induction on employee performance at Abia State Polytechnic. Based on this knowledge gap, his study examines the impact of on-the-job training on employee performance in the public sector, with a specific focus on non-teaching staff at Ambrose Alli University in Edo State, Nigeria. Furthermore, this research uses descriptive and inferential data analysis statistics not used in earlier investigations.

Objectives of the Study

This article analyzes how on-the-job training affects employee performance in the public sector. The precise aims include:

- i. ascertains the impact of induction training on employee job satisfaction in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.
- i. evaluates the impact of job rotation on employee commitment to work in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses of the Study

The following null hypotheses are tested on paper.

- H₀₁: Induction training has no significant impact on employee job satisfaction in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.
- H₀₂: Job rotation has no significant impact on employee commitment to work in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

Training

The term 'training' is widely used in human resource management and development literature, with numerous definitions. Wajdi, et al (2014) define training as a systematic process that involves altering attitudes, behaviors, knowledge, and abilities through learning experiences to achieve effective performance in a variety of tasks. Similarly, Motlokoa, et al (2018) defined training as a deliberate and systematic process of changing behavior through learning

activities and programs that assist participants in acquiring the knowledge, skills, abilities, and competence required to perform their jobs efficiently and successfully.

According to Rodriguez and Walters (2017), training is an organized activity that communicates information and/or instructions to help the recipient improve his or her performance or acquire a required level of knowledge or competence. Training is a learning process that involves acquiring knowledge, honing skills, concepts, and conventions, and altering attitudes and behaviours to improve employee performance (Khan, 2012). This indicates that each occupation is distinct, and employees must possess certain knowledge and abilities to perform their assigned duties. Training is also defined as a set of activities meant to provide individuals with the knowledge, skills, and competence required to increase their performance and organizational productivity. Rashed, *et al* (2019), for example, argued that "training is used to develop the knowledge, abilities, and attitude of employees and that it makes it simpler for employees to acquire further knowledge based on the foundation received from the training and to further affect changes in other coworkers"

Based on the preceding definitions, it can be concluded that training is an indicator of improved abilities, knowledge, capacities, and perspectives among employees, which leads to efficient work performance in the organization. Training improves employee performance, enhances productivity, and helps organizations compete by placing them in the best position to stay at the top (Zahid, 2013). Employee training has numerous benefits for organizations. Training aims to improve not only company performance but also individual growth and performance (Joel & Kelley, 2017). Training increases an organization's profitability or production. This is performed by increasing job knowledge, skill, and morale, which accelerates the attainment of the organization's specified goals (Tahir, *et. al*, 2014)

On-The-Job Training

On-the-job training is described as any learning program provided to an employee in order to perform given activities or obligations while remaining employed. On-the-job training is any sort of training that occurs while an individual is working to learn specific skills and capabilities (Edeh & Nwaji, 2017). On-the-job training is professional coaching that is done in a real-world context to provide employees with the skills needed to complete their assigned tasks. On-the-job training is essential for employees since it enhances their skills, knowledge, competence, abilities, behavior, and attitudes (Malaolu & Ogbuabor, 2013). On-the-job training can be defined as organizational policy training. This word also implies that on-the-job training is a distinct type of job instruction. It focuses solely on teaching the worker the skills required to do a certain profession successfully. This is why it is so widely utilized in organisations. Although this can be done outside of the company, the emphasis on growth is driven by organizational needs. This type of education might be professional or casual. It is formal in the sense that the information to be taught is arranged, ordered, or structured in a logical manner. It becomes informal, however, when employed un-structurally (Malaolu & Ogbuabor, 2013)

Coworkers, supervisors, managers, and mentors frequently provide on-the-job training to assist employees adjust to their new roles and gain the necessary skills (Edeh & Nwaji 2017). On-the-job training may include the following strategies: (1) Job Rotation: In this kind of training, the trainee is transferred from one job to another. (2) Coaching: Each learner is assigned a supervisor who serves as a coach during the training process. (3) Job Instruction: This approach is frequently referred to as "step-by-step training." It is frequently used when an employee is assigned to a new job that she or he has never done before to assess performance and organizational productivity. (4) Committee Assignments: A type of training in which a group of trainees or workers learn how to address a real-world organizational problem as part of a committee project. (5) Apprenticeship: An apprenticeship program teaches you how to perform anything (Edeh & Nwaji, 2017). (6) Induction, often known as orientation, is a sort of training offered by an organization to help new employees get off to a strong start. It is a formal method of introducing new employees to the organization, their job, and their work unit while also instilling organizational values, beliefs, and appropriate behaviours. The benefits include assisting employees in understanding their work environment so that they become productive members of the organization (Agufuana, 2022). On-the-job training is designed according to organizational frameworks. Indeed, it provides trainees with a direct context of the job; it is frequently informal and most successful

since it is learning via experience; it is the least expensive; it is incredibly motivating; and it is free of phony classroom conditions (Edeh & Nwaji, 2017).

Employee Performance

When applied to organizations, the concept of performance is a multi-component term that includes engagement, process, and actual results of a given factor used in the production or service of the organization. Employee performance is defined as the level of development, achievement, or efficiency of work completed by an employee or a group of employees in relation to the expected outcome or output (Rabindra & Lalatendu, 2017). Employee performance is defined as an employee's ability to fulfill a task based on predefined accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed standards (Mvuyis & Mbukanma, 2023) Employee performance has been viewed as an individual output in terms of the process, relevance, and intended outcomes (Nassazi 2013).

According to these definitions, performance includes both behaviour and outcomes. Behaviours stem from performance, which transforms it from abstraction to action. Employee performance is more than simply the instrument for achieving goals; it is also the result of mental and physical effort committed to tasks, which may be quantified based on results. Employee performance is defined as employee task performance, which includes work-specific behaviors identified as important job obligations in the job description (Agufana, 2022). Rabindra and Lalatendu (2017) noted that employee job performance requires more cognitive ability, which is basically facilitated through task knowledge (requisite technical knowledge or principles to ensure job performance and having an ability to handle multiple assignments), task skill (application of technical knowledge to accomplish tasks successfully without much supervision), and task habits (an innate ability to respond to assigned jobs that either facilitate or impede the performance) , which tend to measure the level of employee's job commitment, turn over and satisfaction in organisation.

Theoretical Framework

This work is based on the Job-Demands Resources (JD-R) theory proposed by Arnold B. Bakker and Evangelia Demerouti in 2001. The theory claims that employee job performance is predicted by combining two job characteristics: task demands and personal resources. Job demands are the type of tasks or job that must be completed by the employee, as well as the environment in which such job is performed These include heavy workloads, complicated jobs, workplace conflicts, and the work environment. On the other hand, job resources are those features and circumstances that help employees realize their goals and deal well with job demands. These are learning and development opportunities that may be provided to employees in the organization, such as training and other motivational incentives such as conflict resolution, workplace justice, positive performance reviews, and social support. The JD-R hypothesis proposes that organizations actively pursue job resources by engaging in training and development to meet job needs inside the organization.

The researcher believes that the Job Demands Resources theory is appropriate for this paper since it helps to explain the relationship between employee training and performance. The primary reason for hiring an employee is to involve him in the organization's work process, which draws up tasks or responsibilities that should be assigned to him. No matter what responsibilities are assigned to the employee, such tasks must have certain needs or demands before they can be completed. It could be high-level talents, time, patience, tranquility, tolerance, outspokenness, eloquent speaking, pressure, and so on, depending on the nature of the job. The individual assigned to a job can only complete it efficiently if he possesses the necessary human resources (job attributes). Personal resources, also known as personal job attributes, are obtained through training such as induction, coaching, instructing, mentoring, apprenticeship, work rotation, and others. The inference is that an employee's success in coping with job demands in the company is determined by the quality of personal resources he possesses, which is used to assess his degree of job performance. As

a result, the hypothesis presented in this study suggests that businesses should engage in or begin on staff training, particularly on-the-job training, to improve employees' personal resources and hence their performance.

Empirical Review

Adeba (2019) investigated how on-the-job training impacted employee performance at Wollega University in Ethiopia. The study gathered information through survey research, using a questionnaire distributed to 102 respondents from a sample of 897 University employees. Data was analyzed using percentages, and the findings revealed that on-the-job training improves employee performance in organizations, as trained employees are more committed to their jobs and loyal to the organization than those who do not receive training.

Fernando and Dissanayake (2019) explored how work rotation techniques affect employee job performance in Sri Lanka's private commercial banks. Questionnaires were delivered to 100 operational-level employees from private commercial banks in the Colombo district. The data was examined in SPSS using descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and the Baron and Kenny Mediation Analysis approach. According to the study, job rotation is a critical tool for allowing employees to acquire new talents, boost staff productivity, create new relationships within the firm, and gain skills essential for future career advancement. It also has a good impact on employee job performance.

Agbo (2020) investigated the effects of induction on employee performance at an Abia State Polytechnic. The data was obtained via a questionnaire, and the findings were analyzed descriptively using simple percentages, with the inferential statistic of regression utilized to test the hypothesis. The study discovered that the induction program had a strong and positive relationship with organizational performance. Shamsi (2021) investigated how job rotation practices influenced employee performance in Pakistan's banking sector. A questionnaire was issued to 50 workers from various financial companies. The data was processed using IBM's Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study discovered that job rotation had a large and positive impact on employee performance, motivation, and commitment. The study discovered that job rotation had a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Agufuana (2022) explores the impact of on-the-job training on employee work performance at Kenya's Murang'a University of Technology. The study employed a survey research approach, with 319 university employees separated into two groups: administrative (221) and academic (98). Data was collected using a self-structured questionnaire and then descriptively evaluated using Mean and Standard Deviation. The findings showed that on-the-job training enhances employee job performance.

Mvuyisi and Mbukanma (2023) looked at how on-the-job training affected employee performance among Walter Sisulu University's Integrated Tertiary Software Users. A qualitative method was employed to collect data, with semi-structured interviews conducted with registrar staff and individual university students chosen for the study. Atlas Ti version 9 was used to examine the results. The study discovered that development programs have a direct impact on organizational performance, advancement, and development, all of which are necessary for an effective organization.

Liang, *et al* (2023) explored how job rotation affects employee performance in Chinese state-owned enterprises by providing training, commitment, and development chances. From early 2013 to 2023, the study undertakes a complete and exploratory search of the current literature of various studies, i.e. journals, books, conference papers, and reports related to the topic, to acquire significant information and in-depth insights. The study discovered that job rotation is an effective approach for increasing employee performance in Chinese state-owned firms.

Ezhilarasi, *et al* (2023) investigated the effect of induction training on employee performance using a quantitative approach. Data was collected from a sample of newly hired employees in the organization and examined descriptively with simple percentages and inferentially with Chi-square, ANOVA, and correlation. The results showed that induction training has a positive impact on employee performance within the organisation.

Abdiiaziz (2024) studied the impact of job rotation on employee performance in telecommunications companies in Hargeisa, Somaliland. The study's 95 participants were chosen using a descriptive research methodology using non-probability sampling. The data were examined using the mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation. The study discovered that job rotation improves employee performance.

Research Methods

This paper employed quantitative survey design. A structured questionnaire titled “On-The-Job Training and Employee Performance (OTJTEP)” was designed in 5points Likert scale format of Strongly Agree (SA) = 5 points, Agree (A) = 4 points, Undecided (UD) = 3 points, Disagree (D) =2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point was used to collect data from a sample of 253 respondents selected from 689 Senor Non-teaching Staff members of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. The sample size was determined by Taro Yamane sample size formula (Yamane, 1964) using an error limit of 0.05 and was picked using stratified sampling technique. The face and content validity method were used to validate the instrument while the reliability was established via Pearson Correlation Moment at 0.68 coefficient. The collected data were analysed with Mean Statistic using 2.5 Benchmark score while the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique was utilized for inferential analysis and test of hypotheses using Eviews Computer Software.

To use the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique the following model were specified.

Model One

The model one was used to capture objective one of this study and was stated as:

$$JOBSAT = f(INDUT) \tag{1}$$

The operational form of this model was:

$$JOBSAT_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 INDUT_i + \mu_i \tag{2}$$

- Where, JOBSAT = Job satisfaction
- INDUT = Induction training
- α_0 = Constant Variable
- $\alpha_1 <0 \text{ or} > 0,$ = apriorism expectation
- μ = Stochastic term

Model two for objective two

The functional form of the model was:

$$EMPCMT_i = f(JOBROT) + \varpi_i \tag{3}$$

The operational form of this model was:

$$EMPCMT_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 JOBROT + \varpi_i \tag{4}$$

- Where, EMPCMT = Employee commitment
- JOBROT = Job rotation
- $\beta_0 - \beta_1$ = Parameters to be estimated
- $\beta_1 <0 \text{ or} > 0,$ = apriorism expectation
- ϖ_i = Stochastic term

Data Analysis and Results

In this section, data were analysed descriptively using mean

Table 1: Impact of induction training and employee satisfaction in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Part I Induction training and employee satisfaction to work in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State								
S/N	Statement	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Mean estimation	Mean Score
1	When you are given training as a new employee, you will be exposed to your job roles	50	40	15	30	35	$\frac{550}{170}$	3.2
2	When you are exposed to your new job roles, you will do your work with ease	55	42	13	35	25	$\frac{477}{170}$	2.8

3	When you are given training as a new employee, you will get a good start in the organisation	56	44	10	33	33	$\frac{585}{170}$	3.4
4	When you get a good start in the organisation, you will realize your job objectives	53	40	12	34	31	$\frac{560}{170}$	3.3
5	When you are given training as a new employee, you will embed with organizational values	54	45	12	42	17	$\frac{587}{170}$	3.5
6	When you are embedded with organisational values, you will accomplish the task given to you	58	48	11	35	18	$\frac{603}{170}$	3.5
7	When you are given training as a new employee, you will have a feeling of belongingness to the organisation	53	48	14	26	29	$\frac{580}{170}$	3.4
8	When you feel belonging, you will work adequately in the organisation	52	46	12	34	26	$\frac{574}{170}$	3.4
9	When you are given training as a new employee, the intended benefits you have in the organisation will be revealed to you	56	40	10	35	29	$\frac{569}{170}$	3.4
10	When your intended benefits are revealed to you, you will give your best to the organisation	54	45	12	36	23	$\frac{581}{170}$	3.4

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows the responses on the impact of induction training on employee satisfaction to work in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. The results revealed that out of the ten (10) items, all scored above 2.5 cut-off point of mean; an indication that respondents' viewpoints of induction training is essential for employee satisfaction to work in organisations.

Table 2: Impact of Job rotation on employee commitment to work in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State

Part II Job rotation and employee commitment in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State								
S/N	Statement	SA	A	UD	D	SD	Mean estimation	Mean Score
11	When you have a variety of jobs to do, but each in a certain length of time, your interest in leaving the organisation will be reduced	52	48	15	36	19	$\frac{588}{170}$	3.5
12	When your interest in leaving the organization is reduced, you will be hard working in the organisation.	56	42	13	38	21	$\frac{584}{170}$	3.4
13	When you have a variety of jobs to do, but each in a certain length of time, your absenteeism at work will reduce	50	48	14	36	22	$\frac{578}{170}$	3.4

14	When your absenteeism at work is reduced, your organizational output will increase	60	45	12	40	13	$\frac{609}{170}$	3.6
15	When you have a variety of jobs to do, but each in a certain length of time, your job responsibility will be broadened	58	46	14	30	22	$\frac{598}{170}$	3.5
16	When your job responsibility is broadened, your loyalty to your organisation will increased	55	47	12	36	20	$\frac{591}{170}$	3.5
17	When you have a variety of jobs to do, but each in a certain length of time, you will be zealous to come work early	54	49	10	30	27	$\frac{583}{170}$	3.4
18	When you come to work early, you will do more works than when you came late	52	44	13	38	23	$\frac{574}{170}$	3.4
19	When you have a variety of jobs to do, but each in a certain length of time, you will do over time	56	48	11	36	19	$\frac{596}{170}$	3.5
20	When you are doing over time, the output of your organisation will increase	57	44	12	38	19	$\frac{592}{170}$	3.5

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 shows the responses of the Senior Non-teaching Staff of Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria, to the impact of job rotation on employee commitment to work. The results showed that all ten (10) items investigated scored above the 2.5 cut-off point of the mean, indicating that respondents believe job rotation has an impact on employee commitment to work in the organization.

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Analysis

Model 1

$$JOBSAT_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 INDUT_i + \mu_i$$

$$JOBSAT = 0.249384 + 0.985707INDUT$$

$$t\text{-stat.} = (0.115049) (16.93341)$$

$$R^2 = 0.925744$$

$$R^2 = 0.922516$$

$$F\text{-stat.} = 286.7404$$

$$\text{Critical } t\text{-statistic at } 0.05 \text{ level} = 2.056$$

$$DW \text{ Stat.} = 2.122237$$

The result of model 1 showed that the estimate of the constant is 0.249384. This implied that if the explanatory variable is zero, the dependent variable will be approximately 0.249384.

The estimate of a_1 is 0.985707. This indicated a direct relationship between induction training (INDUT) and job satisfaction (JOBSAT) in Nigeria. It also showed that a unit increase in INDUT will make JOBSAT to increase by 0.985707 in absolute term. However, this relationship is statistically significant as indicated by the empirical t-statistic which is greater than the critical t-statistic (i.e. 16.93341 > 2.056).

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.92574. This suggested that the independent variable can explain 93% of the total variation in the dependent variable. The error term accounts for the unexplained 7 percent fluctuation. The adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.922516. This indicated that the independent variable could explain 92% of the adjusted variation in the dependent variable. The inexplicable variance of 8% is attributable to the error term.

The F-statistic is 286.7404, while the crucial F-statistic at the 0.05 level is 2.60. The empirical F-statistics are bigger than the critical F-statistic, indicating that the explained variance is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The Durbin Watson statistics are 2.122237. According to the rule of thumb, if the Durbin Watson statistic is about two, it indicates that there is no autocorrelation between the subsequent values of the error component.

Model II

$$EMPCMT_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 JOBROT + \varpi_i$$

$$EMPCMT = 1.173867 + 0.953159JOBROT$$

$$t\text{-stat.} = (2.909106) (12.20922)$$

$$R^2 = 0.866330$$

$$R^2 = 0.860518$$

$$F\text{-stat.} = 149.0651$$

$$\text{Critical } t\text{-statistic at } 0.05 \text{ level} = 2.056$$

$$DW \text{ Stat.} = 1.960701$$

The result of model 2 showed that the estimate of the constant (employee commitment to work) is 1.173867. This implies that where the independent variable is zero, the dependent variable is equal to 1.173867.

The job rotation coefficient (JOBSAT) is 0.953159. This implied that job rotation improves employee commitment. As a result, a one-unit increase in job rotation will boost employee job commitment by 0.953159 over time. The empirical t-statistic exceeds the critical t-statistic (12.20922 > 2.056). This indicates that the estimate of β_1 is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.866330. This showed that the independent variable can explain 87 percent of the total variation in the dependent variable. The inexplicable fluctuation of 13% is attributable to the error term. The adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.860518. This indicated that the independent variable could explain 86% of the total variation in the dependent variable. The unexplained adjusted variance of 14% is related to the error term.

The F-statistic is 149.0651, while the crucial F-statistic at the 0.05 level is 2.60. Thus, when the empirical F-statistics are greater than the critical F-statistic, it indicates that the explained variance is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The Durbin Watson statistic equals 1.960701. Based on the rule of thumb, if the Durbin Watson statistic is about two, it indicates that there is no autocorrelation between the subsequent values of the error term.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses, the t-statistic test obtained from Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique was used.

Decision rule: Accept H_0 if the value of calculated t-statistic is greater than the value of critical t-statistic ($t_{cal.} < t_{crit.}$) and rejected if otherwise

Hypothesis One

H_{01} : Induction training has no significant impact on employee job satisfaction in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Table 3: T-statistic of Model One

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INDUCT	0.985707	0.058211	16.93341	0.0000
Critical t-statistic			2.056	

Source: author’s computation from OLS results

According to Table 3, the t-critical value for induction training was 2.056, whereas the t-calculated value was 16.93341 with a matching P-value of 0.0000. The null hypothesis is implied to be rejected since the calculated t-statistic is higher than the t-critical ($16.9 > 2.06$) at the 0.05 level of significance. This showed that at Ambrose Alli University in Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria, induction training significantly affects employee work satisfaction.

Hypothesis Two

H_{02} : Job rotation has no significant impact on employee commitment to work in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Table 4: T-statistic of model two

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
JOBROT	0.953159	0.078069	12.20922	0.0000
Critical t-statistic			2.056	

Source: author’s computation from OLS results

Table 4 showed that the job rotation t-cal. statistic value is 12.20922, with a corresponding P-value of 0.0000 and a t-critical of 2.056. The null hypothesis is thus rejected because, at the 0.05 level of significance, the $t_{cal.} 12.209 > t_{crit} 2.056$. This indicates that employee commitment to work at Ambrose Alli University in Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria, is significantly impacted by job rotation.

Discussion of Findings

Descriptive statistics revealed that all the items on induction training and employee satisfaction scored above

2.5 cut-off means (see Table 1). This showed that induction training has an impact on employee job satisfaction. As shown in Table 3, the estimated t-statistic is higher than the crucial t-statistic ($16.93341 > 2.056$), indicating that the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Regression result in hypothesis one demonstrated that induction training had a significant impact on employee job satisfaction. The results somewhat supported those of Ezhilarasi, Keerthiga, and Roshini (2023), who found that induction training improves employee performance in organizations. Additionally, the results are consistent with Agufuana's (2022) findings that on-the-job training improves employee work performance.

There is a normal distribution score between work rotation and employee commitment in the study, as shown by the descriptive statistic results in Table 2, which demonstrated that all the items used to evaluate the link between the two variables scored over the 2.5 cut-off mean. Additionally, as shown in Table 4, the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) results for hypothesis two demonstrated that the calculated t-statistic was higher than the crucial t-statistic ($12.209 > 2.056$), indicating that job rotation significantly affects employee commitment to work. This result corroborated with the study of Adebaba (2019) that demonstrated the positive effects of on-the-job training on employee performance in an organization. The study found that employees who received training were more devoted to their jobs and loyal to the company than those who did not receive training. The results also supported Abdiaziz's (2024) submission, which found a positive relationship between employee performance and job rotation.

Conclusion

The study concludes that on-the-job training is a tool for improving employee performance in the public sector since the results showed that induction and job rotation significantly and positively affect employee job satisfaction and commitment to work respectively at Ambrose Alli University in Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The paper recommended that state-owned organizations in Nigeria should employ on-the-job training particularly induction and job rotation on regular basis in developing their employees to enhance performance in the public sector.

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Appendix A: Data Variables

JOB SAT	INDUCT EMP CMT	JOB ROT	
55	50	56	52
42	40	42	48
13	15	13	15
35	30	38	36

25	35	21	9
53	56	60	50
40	44	45	48
12	10	12	14
34	33	40	36
31	33	13	22
58	54	55	58
48	45	47	46
11	12	12	14
35	42	36	30
18	17	20	22
52	53	52	54
46	48	44	49
12	14	13	10
34	26	38	30
26	29	23	27
54	56	57	56
45	40	44	48
12	10	12	11
36	35	18	36
23	29	19	19

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Appendix B: OLS Results

MODEL 1

Dependent Variable: JOBSAT

Method: Least Squares

Date: 12/24/24 Time: 08:25

Sample: 1 25

Included observations: 25

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INDUCT	0.985707	0.058211	16.93341	0.0000
C	0.249384	2.167631	0.115049	0.9094
R-squared	0.925744	Mean dependent var	34.00000	
Adjusted R-squared	0.922516	S.D. dependent var	15.30523	
S.E. of regression	4.260362	Akaike info criterion	5.813204	
Sum squared resid	417.4657	Schwarz criterion	5.910714	
Log likelihood	-70.66505	Hannan-Quinn criter.	5.840249	
F-statistic	286.7404	Durbin-Watson stat	2.122237	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

MODEL II

Dependent Variable: EMPCMT

Method: Least Squares

Date: 12/24/24 Time: 11:16

Sample: 1 25

Included observations: 25

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
JOBROT	0.953159	0.078069	12.20922	0.0000
C	1.173867	2.909106	0.403515	0.6903
R-squared	0.866330	Mean dependent var	33.20000	
Adjusted R-squared	0.860518	S.D. dependent var	16.83993	
S.E. of regression	6.289260	Akaike info criterion	6.592182	
Sum squared resid	909.7602	Schwarz criterion	6.689692	
Log likelihood	-80.40228	Hannan-Quinn criter.	6.619227	
F-statistic	149.0651	Durbin-Watson stat	1.960701	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			